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Enhancing Accountability, Quality, and Transparency in Publishing through Global Review and a Negative Citation System.

In recent years, the conventional peer review process has faced growing scrutiny due to the emergence of counterfeit peer-reviewers and a pervasive lack of transparency and accountability. This alarming trend has resulted in instances where new ideas are either stolen or prematurely disclosed in alternative platforms. While the double-blind peer review has been heralded as a potential solution, its real-world implementation has revealed its own imperfections. Therefore, there's a strong need to find new and creative ideas in theory and technology to make the peer review process better and transparent.

A particularly promising proposition lies in the fusion of disruptive technologies such as Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Blockchain. This amalgamation holds the potential to usher in a paradigm shift, transitioning the peer review process from localized evaluations to a globally inclusive model. By strategically identifying and engaging potential expert reviewers from both academia and industry, the risks associated with non-specialists engaging in dishonest publishing practices can be mitigated, thus enhancing the process's integrity.

The combination of AI and Blockchain into the peer review terrain offers a versatile array of implementation routes, presenting a multifaceted approach to holistically enhance the review process. This presentation aims to introduce a comprehensive technological framework that squarely addresses the prevailing malpractices that have insinuated themselves into the review process. Furthermore, the researcher has introduced a negative citation system as an innovative solution to tackle this issue, adding another layer of inspection and accountability.

By take advantage of on AI's capability to pinpoint proficient reviewers and harnessing the inherent transparency of Blockchain to safeguard the process's integrity, a new epoch of peer review emerges- This will create a system that's tough to manipulate and perfectly in tune with the changing demands of the publication world.